

Analysis of Garlic for Its Metal Contents

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Garlic in addition to being a condiment is claimed to have many medicinal properties. Since it is consumed in large quantities the content of metals were analysed which include Zn, Ni, Co, Cr, Fe, Ca, Mg, Cu, K, Na, V, Mo, Ti and Ce and are presented as mg/100 g fresh weight.

GARLIC (*Allium sativum*-Liliaceae) is reported to have antibacterial, antifungal, hypotensive, hypocholesterolemic, antidiabetic, antiinflammatory, anticancer and pesticidal activities¹. It is also claimed to be prophylactic in occupational and chronic lead poisoning^{2,3}. The toxic and therapeutic value of some of the metal elements are convincingly clear from recent reports^{4,5}. Contents of few of these metals from garlic were reported elsewhere⁶⁻¹³. In the present communication, we are reporting the contents of Zn, Ni, Co, Cr, Fe, Ca, Mg, Cu, K, Na, V, Mo, Ti and Ce.

Experimental

After procuring from the market, the cloves devoid of the scales were dried and ashed. 0.5 gram ash was digested under refluxed condenser with a mixture of (1:1) concentrated hydrochloric acid and nitric acid (AR) for two hours and finally centrifuged. The residue was again digested with (1:4) concentrated perchloric acid and hydrochloric acid (AR) for one hour and centrifuged. Both the mother liquors were mixed and finally diluted to 100 ml with 0.1N hydrochloric acid. This solution was used for the estimation of metals. A Varian model AA6 atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used for the estimation of Zn, Ni, Co, Cr, Fe, Mg and Cu. V, Ti, Mo and Ce were estimated colorimetrically¹⁴⁻¹⁷ using Spekol spectrophotometer. Na, K and Ca were estimated with Elico flame photometer.

Results and Discussion

The data for the metal contents obtained from the present investigation are presented in Table 1. The present method for the trace determination of metals is more sensitive compared to the earlier one. In the present investigation the concentration of the metals estimated in the garlic has some discrepancies in values reported by others⁸⁻¹³. The variation may be due to the environmental condition, and the soil in which the plant is growing. The metals reported in the earlier reports by

various workers are; Ni-4.2, Cr-Traces, Cu-0.92, Sr-38.2, Al-2.86 and Mn-Traces mg/100 g fresh weight⁸; Zn-13.8 to 28.9, Fe-98.3 to 263.9, Cu-5.7 to 7.7 and Mn-23.6 to 54.6 ppm in the leaves⁹; Se-0.30 g/100 g fresh weight⁶; Fe-10 to 20 mg/100 g dry weight⁷. Se-90.3 r/100 g fresh weight¹⁰; Mo-42.3 g/100 g fresh weight¹¹; Ca-116 mg, Fe-6, Na-76, K-2112, Mg-36 mg/Lb¹² and Ca-18, Fe-1.5, Na-18 and K-373 mg/100 g edible portion¹³. It can be seen from Table 1 that highest amount of

TABLE 1—METAL CONTENTS OF GARLIC

Sl. No.	Metal	mg/100 g F. Wt.*
1.	Zn	3.961
2.	Ni	0.043
3.	Co	0.028
4.	Cr	0.023
5.	Fe	1.895
6.	Ca	2.687
7.	Mg	17.820
8.	Cu	0.170
9.	K	410.600
10.	Na	8.487
11.	V	0.010
12.	Mo	0.001
13.	Ti	0.001
14.	Ce	Traces

* All the results are a mean of five determinations.

metal found was K (410.6 mg/100 g fresh weight) whereas, Na content is much less (8.487 mg/100 g fresh weight). Next to K garlic contains Mg in a higher amount (17.820 mg/100 g fresh weight). Next to Mg garlic contains Na. Zn is next in the descending order (3.961 mg/100 g fresh weight). Ca is less than Zn (2.687 mg/100 g fresh weight). Fe content also is too less (1.895 mg/100 g fresh weight). All other metals estimated are less than one milligram. Of these metals V and Ni have been found essential for animals, but their essentiality for men have not been proved¹⁸.

Of the various metals reported earlier the content of Sr (38.2 mg/100 g fresh weight⁸) is of great importance. Sr behaves like Ca and follows it into

biological systems. Sr as such is not of much significance to us and is a non-essential element. But radioactive Sr can be a health hazard. Radioactive Sr is becoming widespread in the biosphere as a result of fall out from atomic weapons tests. This Sr⁹⁰ has a long biological residence time as well as a long physical half life. It is a beta emitter which follows Ca metabolically and gets deposited in bone. The radiation emitted could result in bone cancer or leukemia if the levels were to become sufficiently high. Garlic can be considered a potential higher plant accumulating Sr and this can lead to serious health hazard especially in the regions where the radioactive fallout is high in the soil in which the plant grows.

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